

CONCERNS, ISSUES, GAPS AND PROBLEMS (CIGPs) EXPERIENCED BY THE SCHOOL HEADS AND TEACHERS IN ALTERNATIVE DELIVERY MODE INSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed to determine the extent of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and teachers in delivering Alternative Delivery Mode of instructions in all kinds of circumstances in Ayungon Districts 1 and 2 for School Year 2024 - 2025 as basis for an intervention plan. The researchers utilized the descriptive – correlation design of research in investigating the problems specified in this study with the aid of the adapted modified questionnaire as the tool used to gather the data needed. The respondents were the school heads and teachers in all public elementary schools in Ayungon districts 1 and 2. Statistical tools used were weighted mean, Mann Whitney U-test and Kruskal-Wallis test. Findings revealed that the extent of the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and teachers in alternative delivery mode of instructions in all kinds of circumstances is generally “Moderate” in the following areas: learning environment and resources ($\bar{x} = 3.11$); and governance and supervisory management ($\bar{x} = 2.69$). Another salient findings revealed that the p-values showed no significant difference in the extent of the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and teachers in alternative delivery mode of instructions in all kinds of circumstances in each of the aforementioned areas when they are grouped and compared according to their demographic profile variables.

Key Words: *alternative delivery modes, calamities, CIGPs*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, distance learning has emerged as a transformative force in education, reshaping how knowledge is delivered, accessed, and experienced. As technological advancements continue to bridge geographic and temporal barriers, educational institutions worldwide are increasingly adopting distance learning as a viable alternative to traditional face-to-face instruction, especially in times of calamities (Andales, et.al. 2022).

According to Moore and Kearsley (2012), as cited by Kara (2020) in an international dimension to education, all academic institutions choose alternative delivery mode of instruction for a number of reasons such as accessing learning and education, updating skill development, increasing cost effectiveness, increasing the quality of educational structure, improving the capacity of the system of education, balancing inequalities between age groups, providing education to specific target groups, providing emergency training to target groups, expanding the capacity of education in new subject areas, and associating working and family life with education

The commitment of the Department of Education (DepEd) towards Education for All (EFA) as set by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), as well as the attainment of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG), the Philippines is yet confronted with problems on access to quality of basic education. To address these challenges particularly on access, it ventured on Alternative Delivery Modes (ADMs). The Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) aims to provide access to quality basic education for learners who may not be able to attend regular schools due to various circumstances. It includes diverse approaches like homeschooling, online learning, and blended learning, adapting to the specific needs and contexts of different learners (DepEd Order 54, s. 2012; DepEd Memo 047, s. 2024).

There are a lot of studies on the alternative delivery mode but not much has been explored on Concerns, Issues, Gaps and Problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and teachers in terms of evaluation and governance. Thus, this prompted the researchers to do an investigation on these aspects. Furthermore, there are other areas under CIGPs ventured in the present research such as learning environment and resources, teachers' facilitating skills, communication, and feedbacking skills which make this study unique and different from others. Therefore, being a school head in Senior High School level, the researchers is motivated to unfold this study focusing on the (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and teachers in alternative delivery mode of instruction in Ayungon Districts 1 and 2 during the School Year 2024 – 2025 as basis for formulating an intervention plan.

Research Questions

This study was designed to determine the extent of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers in the implementation of the Alternative Delivery Mode instruction during all kinds of circumstances.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. As perceived by the school heads and their teachers, what is the extent of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by them in delivering distance learning instruction during all kinds of circumstances in the following areas:
 - 1.1 learning environment and resources;
 - 1.2 teachers' facilitating skills;
 - 1.3 teachers' evaluation skills;
 - 1.4 communication and feedbacking skills; and
 - 1.5 governance and supervisory management skills?
2. Is there significant difference in the extent of the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers in delivering distance learning instructions during all kinds of circumstances in each of the aforementioned areas when they are grouped and compared according to the following demographic profile variables:
 - 2.1 gender;
 - 2.2 age;
 - 2.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 2.4 position; and
 - 2.5 length of service?

Statement of the Null Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant difference in the extent of the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers in alternative delivery mode of instructions during all kinds of circumstances in each of the aforementioned areas when they are grouped and compared according to the following demographic profile variables:

1. gender;
2. age;
3. highest educational attainment;
4. position; and
5. length of service.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive-correlation method using the modified adapted questionnaire from Garbe, Amber; et. al. (2020) as the main instrument to assess the extent of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers in the implementation of the Alternative Delivery Mode instructions amidst all kinds of circumstances in Ayungon Districts 1 and 2 during the School Year 2024 – 2025.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in all elementary and secondary schools of Ayungon Districts 1 and 2, located in the Division of Negros Oriental, Philippines. Ayungon is situated approximately 82 kilometers north of Dumaguete City, the capital of Negros Oriental.

Ayungon is politically divided into 24 barangays, each consisting of several puroks and, in some cases, sitios. It is classified as a first-class municipality in the northern part of Negros Oriental, with a predominantly rural landscape marked by vast rice fields, dense coconut groves, and extensive plantations of sugar cane, bananas, and pineapples. Agriculture is the primary source of livelihood for most of the approximately 50,000 residents.

Ayungon is administratively divided into two districts: Ayungon District 1 and Ayungon District 2. Each district is overseen by a public school district supervisor. Ayungon District 1 encompasses 18 schools, staffed by 252 teachers and 20 school heads. Meanwhile, Ayungon District 2 comprises several schools with a total of 217 teachers and 20 school heads. This division ensures comprehensive educational administration and supervision within the municipality.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were the 38 school heads and 247 randomly selected teachers of all public elementary, secondary and senior high school levels in Ayungon districts 1 and 2, Negros Oriental Division during the School Year 2024-2025

Statistical Tools

The tools that were used by the researchers in analyzing the data are the following:

Mean: This was utilized in quantifying the extent of the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers.

Mann-Whitney U-Test: This was used to measure the significant difference in the extent of the CIGPs experienced by the school heads and teachers in delivering distance learning instructions during all kinds of circumstances in each of the aforementioned areas when grouped and compared according to gender.

Kruskal-Wallis Test: This was employed to determine the significant difference in the extent of the CIGPs experienced by the school heads and teachers in delivering distance learning instructions during all kinds of circumstances in each of the aforementioned areas when grouped and compared according to age, highest educational attainment, position, and length of service.

Research Instruments

The instrument used in this study is a modified adapted questionnaire from Garbe et al. (2020) to assess the extent of CIGPs experienced by the school heads and their teachers during all kinds of circumstances. It has two parts. The first part is composed of the personal profile of the respondents in terms of age and gender, status, highest educational attainment, and length of service.

The second part is composed of the extent of CIGPs experienced by the school heads and their teachers in the following areas: learning environment and resources, teachers' facilitating skills, teachers' evaluation skills, communication and feedbacking skills, and governance and supervisory management skills.

The contents of the instrument are capsulized from the following sources: Learning Environment and Resources is from Wilson and Peterson (2021); Teachers' Facilitating Skills is from Gagné and Wager (2020); Teachers' Evaluation Skills is from Brookhart (2020); Communication and Feedbacking is from Hattie and Timperley (2007); and Governance and Supervisory Management is from Leithwood and Hopkins (2008).

According to Fraenkel and Wallen (2010), validity refers to the appropriateness, meaningfulness, correctness and usefulness of the inferences a research makes. The questionnaire for the respondents was validated following the criteria. The three validators considered were from the expert instructors and professors of Foundation University. The said experts censored the content, semantics, and syntax of the questionnaire.

The questionnaire was tried-out to test its reliability. A group of school heads and teachers in other schools not included as research respondents were utilized in the try – out. Possible suggestions and corrections after the results of the try – out were considered for improvement purposes. A dry run was conducted to identify item reliability using the Cronbach's Alpha Test. The employment and retrieval of the questionnaires were done personally by the researchers to ensure reliability of responses.

Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

After the research title was approved by the Thesis Committee of Foundation University, the researchers secured permission by addressing a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Negros Oriental, requesting permission to conduct the study with the school heads and teachers in the Ayungon Districts 1 and 2. After receiving approval, the researchers distributed copies to all target schools within the two districts. The researchers personally reached out to the target respondents through district supervisors, school heads, personal phone numbers, school and home visits, and other means. To ensure the reliability of responses, the researchers personally distributed and retrieved the questionnaires.

The gathered data were then sorted, tallied, tabulated, and computed using descriptive and inferential statistics based on the desired categories. The final data were presented in tabular form, analyzed, and interpreted. The findings served as the basis for formulating an intervention plan.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study aimed to examine the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems encountered by school heads and their teachers in the Ayungon 1 and 2 districts during any circumstances throughout the School Year 2024 - 2025. The study focused on five key variables: Learning Environment and Resources, Teachers' Facilitating Skills, Teachers' Evaluation Skills, Communication and Feedbacking Skills, and Governance and Supervisory Management Skills. The respondents consisted of elementary and secondary school heads along with their teachers from the two districts. Several limitations were identified: the diversity in the respondents' backgrounds and life statuses may influence their responses, leading to variability in the assessment of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs). Additionally, the subjective nature of the evaluation, as conducted by both school heads and teachers, could result in differences in perceptions and interpretations. Furthermore, the unique workplace environments of each respondent may affect their perspectives, thereby limiting the consistency of the gathered data.

RESULTS

Table 1. *Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Learning Environment and Resources (n=286)*

I believe that our school has encountered the following problems, gaps, weaknesses, issues, and concerns:	\bar{x}	VD	SD
1. Not all students have gadgets or internet connections available at home for online classes.	4.11	H	1.08
2. Limited dissemination of virtual learning resources due to a lack of technology at home.	3.86	H	1.10
3. Limited utilization of social media platforms like Facebook, YouTube, etc., for teaching and learning purposes.	3.70	H	1.10
4. Reading materials are returned damaged or with missing pages.	3.07	M	0.97
5. Printer malfunctions during printing due to the large number of activity materials per class.	2.92	M	1.05
6. The schedule for retrieving and returning activity materials is not followed by some students.	2.92	M	0.96
7. Insufficient buffer copies of activity materials in case of loss.	2.69	M	0.91
8. Lack of sources for activity materials.	2.67	M	0.95
9. Delayed printing of activity materials.	2.62	M	0.92
10. Insufficient supply of bond paper and ink .	2.52	L	1.06

Composite	3.11	M	1.01
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Note: 4.21–5.00, Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M); 1.81–2.60, Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Very Low (VL)

Table 1 presents that the respondents have a “Moderate” extent of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers in alternative delivery mode instructions in all kinds of circumstances, particularly in the area on learning environment and resources with a composite mean of 3.11.

Table 2. *Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Teachers’ Facilitating Skills (n=286)*

I believe that our school has encountered the following problems, gaps, weaknesses, issues, and concerns:	\bar{x}	VD	SD
1. Struggling to meet the disability-related needs or the gifted and talented needs of learners during distance learning.	3.13	M	1.04
2. Difficulty in maintaining the validity and reliability of answers on the given activity materials.	2.80	M	0.94
3. Struggling to balance household chores with the tasks in the activity materials.	2.77	M	0.86
4. Lack of quality time to encourage learners to think critically and clarify lessons through effective questioning.	2.64	M	0.98
5. Limited knowledge and skills in expressing ideas and discussing topics with learners due to conflicts between study schedules and household chores.	2.52	L	0.99
6. Insufficient ability to apply differentiated instruction in households with more than one learner.	2.51	L	0.93
7. Lack of expertise in using various facilitation techniques, approaches, and strategies to make lessons interesting and meaningful based on learners’ needs, interests, and abilities.	2.48	L	0.90
8. Lack of training in motivating learners through effective questioning to develop critical thinking and creativity.	2.43	L	0.88
9. Lack of preparation in utilizing learning materials that sustain learners’ attention and support teaching objectives.	2.35	L	0.85
10. Inadequate skill in relating lessons to real-life situations and existing conditions convincingly.	2.30	L	0.98
Composite	2.59	L	0.93

Note: 4.21–5.00, Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M); 1.81–2.60, Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Very Low (VL)

Table 2 reflects that the respondents have “Low” extent of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced in alternative delivery mode instructions in all kinds of circumstances particularly in the area on Teachers’ Facilitating Skills with a composite mean of 2.59.

Table 3. Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Teachers' Evaluation Skills (n=286)

I believe that our school has encountered the following problems, gaps, weaknesses, issues, and concerns:	\bar{x}	VD	SD
1. Inadequate provision of evaluative activities appropriate to learners' abilities, interests, and needs.	2.72	M	0.99
2. Limited provision of evaluation results and ratings that are accepted by learners.	2.33	L	0.86
3. Ineffective use of evaluation results as a basis for improving instruction.	2.31	L	0.89
4. Inaccurate grading of learners' performance due to parents or adult family members completing the activities.	2.27	L	0.87
5. Lack of training in using various methods for evaluating learners' progress aligned with learning objectives, such as oral performance, portfolios, hands-on activities, etc.	2.23	L	0.88
6. Given ratings are not aligned with the lesson objectives and the criteria set in the learning materials.	2.20	L	0.86
7. Some learners do not complete the required tasks	2.17	L	0.87
8. Test items are not aligned with the lesson objectives, actual discussions, and activities.	2.15	L	0.90
9. Difficulty in determining awards and recognitions due to the limited basis for evaluating learners' overall performance.	2.13	L	0.87
10. Corrected outputs are not returned to learners regularly.	2.10	L	0.84
Composite	2.26	L	0.88

Note: 4.21–5.00, Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M); 1.81–2.60, Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Very Low (VL)

Table 3 gleans that respondents have “Low” extent of the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers in alternative delivery mode instructions in all kinds of circumstances particularly in the area on Teachers' Evaluation Skills with a composite mean of 2.26.

Table 4. Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Communication and Feedbacking Skills (n=286)

I believe that our school has encountered the following problems, gaps, weaknesses, issues, and concerns:	\bar{x}	VD	SD
1. Occasionally responds to queries from learners and parents due to poor internet connection and signal issues at both the school and home.	2.97	M	0.99
2. Not all parents have cell phones to save teachers' phone numbers, emails, or Facebook accounts.	2.45	L	0.83
3. Does not maintain consistent and continuous communication with parents while engaging with their children.	2.44	L	0.87

4. Only a few parents attend PTA assemblies, conferences, and meetings set by the school due to personal reasons.	2.42	L	1.08
5. Unable to find time to regularly interact with parents and their children.	2.38	L	0.89
6. Unsuccessful in scheduling meetings with parents to discuss their children's progress due to various reasons.	2.32	L	0.88
7. Limited time to connect with parents through home visits due to time management constraints.	2.32	L	0.99
8. Fails to motivate parents to regularly visit the school for feedback purposes.	2.29	L	1.07
9. Limited interaction with parents to gather their comments and suggestions on improving remote instruction.	2.11	L	0.93
10. Rarely monitors or follows up with parents through text, call, or chat.	2.02	L	0.91
Composite	2.37	L	0.94

Note: 4.21–5.00, Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M); 1.81–2.60, Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Very Low (VL)

Table 4. indicates that there is “Low” extent of the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers in alternative delivery mode instructions in all kinds of circumstances particularly in the area on Communication and Feedbacking Skills with a composite mean of 2.37.

Table 5. Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Governance and Supervisory Management (n=286)

I believe that our school has encountered the following problems, gaps, weaknesses, issues, and concerns:	\bar{x}	VD	SD
1. Fails to allocate sufficient time for learning activities.	3.38	M	1.11
2. Lacks patience with learners.	2.85	M	0.92
3. Lacks consistency in assisting learners with their tasks.	2.78	M	0.98
4. Unable to achieve the objectives set for the day with learners.	2.77	M	1.04
5. Does not maintain learners' positive behavior as expected.	2.69	M	1.03
6. Fails to establish authority effectively during discussions by ensuring learners follow the rules.	2.55	L	0.98
7. Lacks the ability to create active interactions that make learning enjoyable.	2.47	L	0.97
8. Unable to sustain learners' interest in lessons and discussions.	2.45	L	0.93
9. Lacks initiative to develop instructional strategies and supervisory interventions to improve learning at home.	2.41	L	0.98
10. Challenged in demonstrating patience toward learners.	2.38	L	0.96
Composite	2.69	M	0.99

Note: 4.21–5.00, Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M);

1.81–2.60, Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Very Low (VL)

Table 5 exhibits “moderate” extent of the concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the school heads and their teachers in alternative delivery mode instructions in all kinds of circumstances particularly in the area of Governance and Supervisory Management with a composite mean of 2.69.

Table 6. *Difference in the Extent of CIGPs of the Respondents in Alternative delivery mode instructions during Calamities when Grouped according to Their Profile*

Variables	n	Median	Comp.	p	Decision	Remark
Gender						
			U-value			
Male	55	2.54	6279	0.895	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
Female	231	2.54				
			F-value			
Age						
21 – 30	48	2.43	2.170	0.538	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
31 – 40	113	2.54				
41 – 50	75	2.62				
41 – 50	50	2.58				
Educational Attainment						
Bachelor’s Degree	126	2.58	2.573	0.462	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
w/ Master’s Deg. Units	132	2.51				
w/ Master’s Degree	18	2.56				
w/ Doc. Deg./Units	10	2.23				
Position						
T-I	67	2.58	1.625	0.654	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
T-II	62	2.49				
T-III	123	2.54				
MT/ P	34	2.58				
Length of Service						
1 – 5 years	57	2.50	4.541	0.338	Fail to reject H ₀	Not significant
6 – 10 years	84	2.53				
11 – 15 years	48	2.63				
16 – 20 years	43	2.38				
>20 years	54	2.75				

The results in Table 6 indicate that there is no significant difference in the extent of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) experienced by the respondents in alternative delivery mode instructions during calamities when grouped according to demographic variables such as gender, age, educational attainment, position, and length of service.

DISCUSSION

Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Learning Environment and Resources

One of the top problems in delivering distant learning described as “High” is technology at home as indicated in the lack of learner’s gadgets or no or slow internet connections for online classes ($\bar{x} = 4.11$) and limited access on virtual learning resources ($\bar{x} = 3.86$). The importance of these is emphasized by the findings of Dolan (2016) when they said that internet coverage and availability of computers or smartphones are essential needs for remote learning, and thus lack of reliable infrastructure and devices increased parents’ struggles with remote learning.

Furthermore, because of lack of technology and slow internet connectivity, the use of various social media platforms ($\bar{x} = 3.70$) and other educational software would be impossible as this is also described as “High” in the table. This is supported by Greenhow and Lewin (2016) when they stressed out that social media has become an integral part of the teaching and learning process, offering numerous benefits that can enhance educational experiences for learners. It allows for real-time communication between students and teachers, making it easier to clarify doubts and receive feedback. Platforms like Facebook, YouTube, TikTok, WhatsApp, or specialized educational tools facilitate group discussions, project collaboration, and peer learning, regardless of geographical barriers.

Moreover, the table also reveals that the school heads and their teachers have experienced several concerns, issues, gaps and problems in the following areas with “Moderate” categories: damaged reading materials ($\bar{x} = 3.07$); malfunctioned printer ($\bar{x} = 2.92$); unfollowed schedule of retrieval and return of activity materials ($w\bar{x} = 2.92$); and insufficient buffer copies ($\bar{x} = 2.69$). Printers play a significant role in distance learning, particularly in the context of creating buffer copies of learning modules. Instructors can provide printed tests, quizzes, and assignments, offering students a more traditional learning and assessment method. Learners can bring all printed activity materials at home but not all of them can cope with the deadline due to delays in answering them caused by lack of gadgets and internet for research at home.

Finally, other concerns, issues, gaps and problems considered by the school head and their teachers described as “Low” to “Moderate” are the following: Insufficient supply of bond paper and ink ($\bar{x} = 2.52$); delayed printing ($\bar{x} = 2.62$); and lack of sources of activity materials ($\bar{x} = 2.67$). These three CIGP areas seemed to be manageable by the school heads and their teachers since the school has financial capacity to resolve any problem that would occur under these.

Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Teachers' Facilitating Skills

As exposed on Table 2, items 1 to 4 are rated by the respondents as “Moderate” concerns, issues, gaps and problems. These were: disability-related needs or the gifted and talented needs ($\bar{x} = 3.13$) as ranked 1, then followed by validity and reliability of answers ($\bar{x} = 2.80$), balance household chores ($\bar{x} = 2.77$), and quality time ($\bar{x} = 2.64$). The rank 1 is in congruence with the citation of Gagné and Wager (2020) where they found out that teachers should be skilled in adapting content for diverse learner needs, particularly during crises, ensuring accessibility and learner engagement despite external disruptions.

Moreover, the table divulges some concerns, issues, gaps and problems described as “Low” from indicators 5 to 10. These were: expressing ideas and discussing topics ($\bar{x} = 2.52$); differentiated instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.51$); facilitation techniques, approaches, and strategies ($\bar{x} = 2.48$); motivating learners ($\bar{x} = 2.43$); learning materials ($\bar{x} = 2.35$); and relating lessons to real-life situations and existing conditions ($\bar{x} = 2.30$). The findings imply that school heads and their teachers need to consider best practices, strategies and motivations which can be acquired through training. This is supported by Fernandez and Shaw (2020) when they recommended that academic head and their teachers shall focus on best practices, try to see opportunities in the crisis, communicate clearly, connect with others, and distribute head and their teacherships within the organization.

The overall findings of composite 2.59 described as “Low” imply that there are other factors that might influence the extent of concerns, issues, gaps, and problems experienced by the school heads and their teachers. Some of these might be what O’Doherty, et. al. (2018) have stated that distant learning might be influenced by the following factors: time limitations, weak technical skills, inadequate infrastructure, lack of institutional strategies and support and negative attitudes of everyone involved, lack of high-speed internet and durable technology, lack of trainer and learner skills and lack of support services.

The finding is also related to the findings of Rasmitadila et al. (2020) when they found out that teachers face problems in distance education implemented in the calamities such as technical barriers, learner’s conditioning, learner’s participation in education and online education experience.

Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Teachers' Evaluation Skills

As purported in Table 3, almost all the indicators belonged to “Low” category in all areas as evident of the values of the weighted means ranging within 1.81 – 2.60. These are: evaluation results and ratings ($\bar{x} = 2.33$); evaluation results as a basis for improving instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.31$); grading of learners’ performance ($\bar{x} = 2.27$); various methods for evaluating learners’ progress ($\bar{x} = 2.23$); giving ratings ($\bar{x} = 2.20$); required tasks ($\bar{x} = 2.17$); lesson objectives, actual discussions, and activities ($\bar{x} = 2.15$); awards and recognitions

(\bar{x} =2.13); outputs (\bar{x} =2.10). These findings imply that the school heads and their teachers found these areas very manageable during all kinds of calamities. This could mean that the distant delivery mode due to any kind of circumstance would not be severely affected by these CIGP factors since any of these could be done without too much preparations and considerations.

However, it could be noticed, that 1 among the 10 indicators was described as “Moderate.” This indicator is on: inadequate provision of evaluative activities appropriate to learners’ abilities, interests, and needs with a weighted mean of 2.72. This could be attributed to the fact that not all evaluative activities could be done online or printed materials. Some could be done through actual performance and group presentations which could be difficult to do during distant learning. During alternative learning mode of instructions, learners will have negative habits by decreasing their motivation to learn. Learners have not answered the activities in the printed materials. Some of them have let their parents or older sisters and brothers answer their printed materials. As a result, evaluating their performance will not be significant. Teachers will find it difficult to determine their actual achievement and performance.

Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Communication and Feedbacking Skills

As seen in Table 4, the school heads and their teachers’ concerns, issues, gaps, and problems (CIGPs) gets ‘Moderate’ rating (\bar{x} = 2.97) specifically on poor internet connection and signal issues. This signifies that the learners and parents have difficulties in communicating with the teachers due to poor internet connection and signal issues at both the school and home. This is in line with the research of Fauzi et al. (2020) when they revealed that teachers face problems during calamities such as lack of opportunities, network and internet use, planning, implementation and evaluation of learning, and collaboration with parents.

On the other hand, the rest of the indicators of Communication and Feedbacking Skills from items 2-10 falls under “Low” category. These are: availability of parents’ cell phones (\bar{x} =2.45); continuous communication with parents (\bar{x} =2.44); PTA assemblies, conferences, and meetings (\bar{x} = 2.42); interact with parents and their children (\bar{x} =2.38); scheduling meetings with parents (\bar{x} =2.32); connect with parents through home visits (\bar{x} =2.32); visit the school for feedback purposes (\bar{x} =2.29); interaction with parents to gather their comments and suggestions (\bar{x} = 2.11); and monitors or follows up with parents through text, call, or chat (\bar{x} =2.02). These findings could mean that communicating and feedbacking with parents are not treated as serious problems by the school heads and their teachers in the success of distant teaching and learning activities. This further connotes that interactions with parents and the school alone cannot be a problem since both have enough time to meet as needed. The availability of parents in schools during various calamities such as natural disasters, health crises, or emergencies plays a crucial role in ensuring the safety and well-being of learners. Parents should receive ongoing information during a calamity to stay informed about their child’s safety and the school’s response.

Extent of CIGPs Experienced by the Respondents in Terms of Governance and Supervisory Management

The school heads and their teachers' concerns, issues, gaps, and problems are rated to be "Moderate" in terms of time for learning activities ($\bar{x}=3.38$); patience with learners ($\bar{x}=2.85$); assisting learners with their tasks ($\bar{x}=2.78$); objectives set for the day with learners ($\bar{x}=2.77$); and learners' positive behavior as expected ($\bar{x}=2.69$).

This finding highlights the avicritical factor for schools to create an interaction between learners and teachers and to provide psychological guidance along with providing education materials and distance education for learners during crisis. This is supported by Leithwood and colleagues (2019) when they emphasized that effective governance and leadership are crucial during times of crisis and other circumstances.

In addition, other remaining indicators of Governance and Supervisory Management belong to "Low" category which could mean that the school heads and their teachers are able to handle matters appertaining thereto. According to Netolicky (2020) that leaders during calamities should provide clear guidance, support teachers' professional development in remote learning, and ensure that schools have the infrastructure and resources needed for online instruction.

Difference in the Extent of CIGPs of the Respondents in Alternative Delivery Mode Instructions during Calamities when Grouped according to Their Profile

It is divulged for gender, that both male and female respondents have the same median score (2.54), and a p-value of 0.895. This finding suggests that the difference is not statistically significant. Similarly, after computing Kruskal-Wallis Test across different age groups, the median scores range from 2.43 to 2.62, a p-value of 0.538, indicating no significant difference. These findings on across different ages have lots of implications. To name a few, older teachers often have decades of experience and a wealth of knowledge about pedagogical practices, school policies, and crisis management. They may have witnessed or experienced various calamities throughout their careers, shaping their perceptions of risks and necessary responses while younger teachers may lack extensive experience but often bring fresh ideas and approaches to teaching. Their perceptions may be influenced by their recent training, which may emphasize modern teaching techniques and digital tools for crisis management.

The finding is also expounded by Jacinto and Ochotorena (2023) when he stated that older teachers may feel less comfortable with newer technologies, which can impact their ability to adapt to online or hybrid learning during emergencies. They may see gaps related to their skills or the technology support available at their schools. Younger teachers are typically more adept at utilizing technology, enabling them to better navigate crises by leveraging digital resources for teaching and communication. They may identify problems related to inequities in access to technology among students or training in its use.

Jacinto and Ochotorena (2023) added that older teachers may favor traditional approaches to crisis management, relying on established protocols and face-to-face communication. They might perceive gaps in preparedness based on their experiences with previous crises. Younger teachers often advocate for innovative and flexible approaches to crisis management, emphasizing adaptability, collaboration, and the incorporation of social media for timely communication. They may view problems related to a lack of rapid response systems or insufficient mental health support for students. Regarding educational attainment, while the median scores varied slightly, the computed p-value of 0.462 shows no significant variation. Likewise, respondents holding different positions (Teacher I, II, III, and Master Teacher/Principal) have median scores between 2.49 and 2.58, with a p-value of 0.654, failing to establish a significant difference. Lee and Rodriguez (2018) contrasted these findings, suggesting that individuals with advanced degrees possess the advanced knowledge in crisis management, educational leadership, and psychology necessary for effective emergency decision-making. Conversely, they note that those with lower educational attainment may lack familiarity with strategic planning and resource allocation needed during crises. They also highlighted that higher educational attainment often correlates with greater access to specialized training and professional development, leading to better preparedness.

Lastly, length of service also do not yield any significant difference, despite variations in median scores from 2.38 to 2.75. The p-value (0.338) indicates that experience in years does not significantly impact the extent of challenges faced in distance learning instruction during calamities. This point is further supported by Johnson and Smith (2020), who discovered that novice teachers and school heads (those with limited experience) were less effective than veteran educators (those with extensive experience) in comprehending their perceptions of teaching challenges during disasters. Their research also indicates that teachers' crisis management skills, preparedness, and confidence in handling classroom disruptions are influenced by their educational level and position.

Synthesizing the results, the findings suggest that demographic factors do not play a significant role in determining the extent of CIGPs encountered by school heads and their teachers during alternative delivery mode of instructions. This implies that external factors beyond individual demographic characteristics may be more influential in shaping the challenges faced in such scenarios. This is more discussed by Reyes and Garcia (2019) when they exposed that issues in schools often arise from multiple interconnected factors (e.g., school policies, community engagement, resource availability) rather than simply demographic characteristics. This complexity makes it difficult to pinpoint demographic factors as significant causes. They further stated that learners and educators may experience similar challenges (e.g., bullying, academic pressure, lack of resources) regardless of their demographic backgrounds. This shared experience can mask demographic disparities. They also added that schools that provide comprehensive support systems like counselling services, tutoring, and extracurricular programs can mitigate the effects of demographic differences. If robust support is available, the relevance of demographic factors diminishes. Lastly, they discussed that the way a school is managed, its policies, and its overall environment can have a more substantial impact

on issues and problems than the demographics of its students and staff. Inclusive policies and practices can lead to similar outcomes across diverse demographic groups.

Conclusions

The result of the study mirrors the resiliency of school heads and teachers. As resiliency theory argues that when one is resilient, it is not the nature of adversity that is most important, but it is how one is able to deal with it, bounce back, survive and recover life's adversities. The Concerns, Issues, Gaps and Problems (CIGPs) that the teachers and school heads experience in different areas show different extent of difficulty as revealed in the study. Responses to these CIGPs vary from one person's perspectives and experience.

The early experience of these CIGPs caught every school head and teacher flat-footed but with mechanisms designed by the DepEd to avert and mitigate effects of these CIGPs, continuity and learning is ensured and at the same time promotion of welfare, safety and security of learners as well as of the personnel at all times are ensured. Considered as the paramount concern of the DepEd, the agency issued DepEd Order No. 22, s, 2024.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended to address the various concerns, issues, gaps, and problems prevalent in schools. It is essential to initiate in-service training tailored to the specific needs of each institution. Such training will ensure that challenges are met proactively and effectively. Additionally, developing instructional innovations can significantly enhance teaching practices, addressing the diverse educational needs of teachers. Utilizing the action plans submitted by master teachers and other potential educators will further enrich instructional strategies, fostering a more collaborative and dynamic teaching environment.

It is also recommended to revisit Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) plans, ensuring they are aligned with current challenges and effectively resolve various CIGPs (Concerns, Issues, Gaps, and Problems). Prioritizing these CIGPs based on urgency, necessity, and potential benefits will optimize resource allocation and response strategies. Empowering teachers to independently address classroom-level CIGPs will build resilience and problem-solving capacity within the teaching community. Additionally, establishing partnerships with stakeholders who are willing to support the school in diverse aspects will strengthen community involvement and resource availability.

Furthermore, teachers should take the initiative to update their personal and professional development plans regularly, ensuring they remain aligned with evolving educational demands. Creating innovative approaches to resolve classroom-specific CIGPs will also enhance the learning environment. Collaborating with classroom PTA officers on future plans and projects will build a stronger sense of community and support within the school.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, the researchers adhered to ethical guidelines and ensured full compliance with the principles of informed consent. All participants were fully informed about the nature of the study, the objectives, and the procedures involved. They were made aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or loss of benefits. Anonymity was guaranteed to all respondents, and personal information was kept confidential throughout the study. The well-being of the participants was prioritized, ensuring that their participation did not cause any harm or discomfort.

Furthermore, no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study, as the researchers had no personal or financial stakes in the outcomes. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were appropriately cited. The interpretation of the findings was carried out impartially and without bias. Finally, the results of the study were used solely for research purposes, with the aim of contributing to the enhancement of instructional practices in grammar education.

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